

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, the expressions of pedagogical technologies, educational technology, teaching technology are often mentioned in the current pedagogical science. To date, in the pedagogical literature, reports on educational problems, in official documents, the concepts of "new pedagogical technology", "advanced pedagogical technology", "modern educational technology" have not yet been put into one mold, as has been explained in encyclopedias, a single interpretation of its content has not been developed, and therefore there are many definitions of the phrase that differ from each other. Opinions and comments on the role of pedagogical technologies in improving the quality of training are made.

Keywords: education, technology, pedagogy, quality, teaching, modern, information.

Pedagogical technology is such a sphere of knowledge that in the third millennium of the state in its policy in the field of education there will be a radical turn, teacher activity will be renewed, a system of feelings of freedom, thirst for knowledge, love for the motherland, love for students and students will be formed.

The main idea, which lies on the basis of knowledge, is also considered to be humane, which rejects the authoritarian and false way of thinking, which understands the unity of nature and man, is patient, content, respects the opinion of others, provides for the formation of personal qualities, such as national-cultural and universal values. The solution of this issue is to a certain extent correlate education with technological development.

Let's first clarify the concept of "technology". This word came into science in 1872 in connection with technical progress, and from the Greek two words (techno) - art, skill, craft and logos (logos) - means "science of skill", formed from the words science. However, this expression, too, cannot fully characterize the modern technological process. The technological process assumes the execution of operations in a certain sequence, always using the necessary tools and conditions. To be more precise, the technological process is the activity of a worker (working machine) on the creation of products as a result of a gradual

exposure to Labor objects (raw materials) with Labor weapons. If we turn this definition to the topic of research, namely: pedagogical technology is the process by which the teacher (educator) with the help of educational means influences the students (students) in certain conditions, and the formation in them of previously defined personal qualities as the product of this activity.

As can be seen from the above description, the process of technology was based on the interpretation of the concept of pedagogical technology. In fact, the definitions given to this concept are incredibly numerous in the pedagogical literature. In pedagogical literature, it is possible to meet a variety of manifestations of the term "technology": "educational technology", "educational technology", "information technology", "educational process technology", etc. Although teaching technology is a concept close to pedagogical technology, it does not mean exactly the same, because it expresses the way of mastering a specific teaching material within a given subject, subject and questions around a particular technology. It stands alongside more private methodology.

And pedagogical technology represents the tactics of introducing Information Technology and is built on the knowledge relevant to the laws of the functional system "teacher - pedagogical process pupil (student)". It is worth noting that at the same time there is no single opinion on the logical-ideological interpretation of the concept of educational technology. In the pedagogical literature, more than 300 definitions are given.

As already mentioned above, although the theory of pedagogical technology is based on it from the second half of the last century, there are different approaches to the concept of "pedagogical technology". In particular, the pedagogical scientist V. P. Bepalko describes pedagogical technology as "a project of a certain pedagogical system that will be applied to practice", and focuses the main attention on the preliminary design of the educational-pedagogical process. N. F. Talzina notes that pedagogical technology should be "an independent science aimed at solving such issues as the production of methods that promote a certain principle in the range of Science and practice, the consistent application of them," etc.

One of the directions that is currently developing widely in the field of education is the use of modern pedagogical technologies. It is known that the educational process consists in the teaching of the older generation of their knowledge and experience to the growing generation, in this process, the transmission of information necessary mainly for human life from generation to generation is carried out. There are different definitions of pedagogical

technology, each definition represents an approach from a certain point of view. Let's look at some basic definitions and their interpretations. Pedagogical technology is the activity of formation of a harmonious person. Technology is the sum of methods, ways used in a work, skill, art. Technology is the collection of processing, the art of changing the situation, skills, abilities, methods. Pedagogical technology is a complex of psychological procedures, which determines the totality and component (location) of teaching, forms of education, methods, methods, Pathways, Educational means: it consists of organizational and methodological tools of the pedagogical process.

In conclusion, pedagogical technology is a new approach to teaching. It is the expression of the socio-engineering thinking in pedagogy, the transferred image of the techno-scientific consciousness to the pedagogical sphere, the specific standardization of the educational process. From the mutual diversity of some of the above definitions, it can be seen that the concept of pedagogical technology is multifaceted, and it can be approached from a pedagogical, psychological, didactic, organizational, economic, social, environmental and other points of view

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